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Quality Reading: Mechanism for Developing of Self-Defense Reading Strategies Against Disinformation Publications in Digital Media

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The object of this paper is the relation between the spread of disinformation in digital media and the possibility for deep reading from screen.

The main problem: exploring whether the algorithm of reading from screen of texts, containing disinformation, hinders their due critical perception.

Purpose of the study: To prove that such a relation exists and to describe it from the perspective of the media theory of reading, a fundamental scientific field regarding the manner, in which textual information is being perceived.

Methodology/approach: The applied methodology includes the tools of the theory of communication and the media theory of reading, bibliographic search methods, bibliographic information retrieval and modelling. The qualitative systematic review, methods of analytic and synthetic processing of primary and secondary resources and SWOT analysis, as well as the results, summarized in the 2018 COST E-READ Stavanger Declaration, have all been used for this paper.

Hypothesis: a fundamental problem regarding the spread of disinformation through digital publications is that the readers of

written media content use a distorted algorithm of reading, which doesn't allow for the possibility of critical examination and analysis of the perceived information.

Results: the particular aspects of the discussed distorted algorithm of reading would be revealed and analysed and a mechanism for prevention and self-defense against disinformation and misinformation digital publications would be proposed for the expert adult readers.

Implications: educational strategies would be developed, enhancing deep reading from screen as a tool for fighting the problem of the spread of disinformation in digital media.